

Flexible photovoltaic generation strategy for Rome Technopole[☆]Gianluigi Bovesecchi^a, Federico Andreozzi^a, Marcello Petitta^b, Marco Pierro^c, Richard Perez^d, Cristina Cornaro^{a,*}^a Department of Enterprise Engineering, University of Rome Tor Vergata, 00133 Rome, Italy^b Department of Mathematics and Physics, Roma Tre University, 00146 Rome, Italy^c Institute for Renewable Energy – EURAC, 39100 Bolzano, Italy^d Atmospheric Sciences Research Center, University at Albany, Albany 12222 NY, United States

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ABSTRACT

As part of Italy's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), the "Rome Technopole" innovation ecosystem focuses on Energy Transition. Within this initiative, the RES4TECH project aims to meet the electricity demand of the future Rome Technopole campus through energy-flexible photovoltaic (PV) systems with battery energy storage systems (BESS).

These energy-flexible PV systems with BESS, integrated with smart inverters and remote control, are designed to deliver power reliably under two scenarios: one delivering forecasted generation, and the other matching a continuous demand profile (24/365 firm generation). Since the Rome Technopole will be completed by 2030, the expected electrical load was modeled using data from the Engineering Macro-area at the University of Rome Tor Vergata (2013–2021). Solar and climate data from the university's EsterLab enabled simulations of PV generation at various tilt angles, identifying 30° south-facing as optimal.

An optimization process was developed to determine the ideal balance between PV and BESS capacity to minimize energy costs. Simulations show that oversizing PV capacity (3.9 times the annual electrical demand) and integrating storage can fully cover electricity needs. The optimal system includes 9.5 MWp of PV and 16.8 MWh of storage to serve an average daily demand of 9.84 MWh.

A financial analysis indicates that 65 % self-production is already cost-effective today (LCOE = 112 €/MWh, payback period = 11 years). Achieving 80 % self-generation would currently require 28 years, but this could drop to 9 years if 2050 technology costs are reached by 2030.

Introduction

Solar energy plays a central role in energy transition and has experienced rapid growth. As highlighted in a recent report by the Fraunhofer Institute [1], the photovoltaic industry is developing under a multitude of aspects. From the technological standpoint, PV cells continue to improve in efficiency, and new materials such as perovskite are emerging. These advancements have led to a significant drop in prices and a steady increase in installed capacity, which reached 2156.5 GWp at the end of 2024. Moreover, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has become a standard practice in PV system design, emphasizing sustainability indicators like Energy Payback Time (EPBT) and promoting attention to resource usage and recyclability. Ahmed [2] offers a comprehensive overview of the 2025 PV landscape, highlighting

innovative applications such as agrivoltaics, microgrids, and energy communities, while also addressing critical challenges like the sector's continued reliance on fossil fuels and outdated legislation.

The term "firm power generation" is generally associated with a strategy able to continuously supply a specified electricity demand 24/365. Therefore, it is particularly important that any power grid incorporates an adequate mix of energy sources in order to be defined "firm", meaning reliable in continuously providing power. Perez et al. [3] propose a comprehensive framework to achieve firm solar power generation by combining overbuilding, curtailment, and energy storage, emphasizing that this strategy not only eliminates supply uncertainty but also represents the most cost-effective pathway to enable ultra-high solar penetration.

To date, this mix includes thermal generation (mostly derived from fossil fuels), nuclear power (where viable from a legal perspective,

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Nomenclature			
AEMO	Australia Energy Market Operator	NPV	Net Present Value
ARPA	Regional Agency for Environmental Protection	NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
BESS	Battery Energy Storage Systems	NYISO	New York Independent System Operator
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service	OVS	Oversize
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure	P	Power
CNR	National Research Council	PBP	Payback Period
d	day	PEIROCOM	Pan-European Intermittent Renewable Overbuilding and Curtailment Optimization Model
ERAA	European Resource Adequacy Assessment	PNRR	National Recovery and Resilience Plan
GHI	Global Horizontal Irradiance	PUN	National Unique Price
h	hour	PV	Photovoltaic
IRR	Internal Rate of Return	RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy	SP	Self-production
LCOE _{firm}	Levelized Cost of Energy of firm PV generation	T	temperature
LCO-PV	Levelized Cost of PV	TSO	Transmission System Operator
LCOS	Levelized Cost of Storage	VRE	Variable Renewable Energy
MISO	Midcontinent Independent System Operator	w	week
NDY	Number of daily electric demand to be stored	WACC	Weighted Average Cost of Capital

which is not the case for Italy) and hydropower (which depends on the availability of water and can thus be severely hindered in drought conditions). Variable Renewable Energy (VRE) sources, such as solar and wind power, are generally sidelined to a secondary role due to their inherent intermittency and inability to provide a steady, on-demand supply. In most cases, systems based mainly or exclusively on VRE cannot be considered “firm” under current strategies, rendering them an unviable option for continuous power generation.

As an example, data from Terna, the Italian Transmission System Operator, suggests that in 2022, Italy’s energy production relied 49.66 % on thermal generation, 19.26 % on hydropower, 20.44 % on solar, 9.88 % on wind power and 0.76 % on geothermal sources [4].

In the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic, themes such as carbon neutrality and environmentally friendly technologies have risen to a new level of attention among European institutions. Within this framework, the EU has defined and published the NextGenerationEU recovery plan. This initiative provides guidance and funding for projects focusing on energy transition, among other things. In response to this European Community initiative, the Italian government has formulated the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) [2], which is divided into six missions:

1. Digital transition, innovation, competitiveness, culture and tourism
2. Green revolution and ecological transition
3. Infrastructures for sustainable mobility
4. Education and research
5. Inclusion and cohesion
6. Health

The increasing penetration of Variable Renewable Energy (VRE) sources, primarily solar and wind, presents a significant challenge to the current power generation paradigm. To integrate these fluctuating resources effectively, a fundamental strategic shift is required. We must move VRE from a marginal role to a foundation of our power generation mix. This transformation, often termed the energy transition, hinges on the ability of VRE to become a dispatchable resource. Achieving this objective requires ensuring VRE output closely aligns with electricity demand profiles while effectively managing inherent forecasting uncertainties.

According to Liu et al. [5], the key enablers for this shift in the PV field are energy storage systems (ESSs), PV overbuilding and curtailment, and PV forecasting. Their study outlines research directions for making PV dispatchable and proposes a roadmap combining these

enablers to reach that goal.

Kaledio & Favour [6] explore ESS options such as thermal storage, pumped hydro, compressed air, and battery energy storage systems (BESS). They emphasize that proper sizing and system configuration are crucial to maximize energy yield, ensure grid stability, and maintain economic viability, a core focus of the present study. Furthermore, studies [7–9] underscore the role of BESS in improving distribution system performance, particularly in voltage regulation, peak demand shaving, and power loss reduction. These studies compare different control algorithms to assess BESS impacts on these parameters and overall system cost. The consensus is that BESS improves system performance, with multi-unit deployment increasing effectiveness—albeit at higher cost.

With respect to system sizing, Tejero-Gomez et al. [10] conducted large-scale, long-term simulations to identify the optimal PV-BESS configuration for continuous power delivery. They introduce energy unavailability indicators to guide system planning and identify a “critical storage zone” beyond which further increases in battery capacity offer negligible improvements. This zone represents a practical optimum, highlighting the need to avoid oversizing storage unnecessarily. An early work from Budischak et al. [11] concluded that a strategy involving both traditional energy storage (e. g. in the form of Battery Energy Storage Systems, or BESS) and excess capacity (what will later be defined “implicit storage”) is the approach that gives the most promising results even from a system cost viewpoint. This is of utmost importance, as for a change of mentality to be widely accepted, it needs to be economically attractive, meaning that it must produce a tangible reduction in the total cost of energy compared to the current status.

The previously mentioned concept of implicit storage is defined as the combination of overbuilding and pro-active curtailment used to limit the amount of traditional energy storage needed to meet the electricity demand, thus keeping costs at reasonably low level [12].

Curtailment is often viewed as a loss [13,14], simply because of its definition as a “reduction in system output”. In fact, Micheli et al. [15], while analyzing the economic effects of curtailment in high-PV-penetration markets, point out that, under current intraday market regulations, excessive curtailment could make PV projects economically unfeasible. Under this premise, looking at curtailment as a measure to enhance efficiency might seem counter intuitive. However, as underlined by O’Shaughnessy et al. [13,14], redefining curtailment as “unused system output” might render the needed shift of thinking easier, enabling policymakers and grid operators to eventually use firm VRE systems to their full potential, which is made much more apparent in this

definition. As the penetration of VRE inevitably grows, the focus will shift to seeking the optimal level of curtailment, rather than to minimize it. The Italian framework is particularly of interest for this study. In this context, the work by Pierro et al. [16] presents a strategy to gradually increase penetration of RES, setting 2060 as the target for a complete and economically feasible solar/wind transition. This goal is to be reached by gradually extending the flexible plants' duty cycle until firm power generation is achieved, and VRE can meet the Italian grid demand 24/365. This will be possible, the authors state, by overbuilding and proactively curtailing the resulting overgeneration, which will also allow for this strategy to be cost-effective. Drawing a roadmap for the transition to VRE is a particularly interesting approach, which was replicated in our research and applied to our case. Specifically, Bovesecchi et al. [17] demonstrate the feasibility of achieving 90 % self-production in the Lazio region by 2050 through the installation of 34.73 GWp of photovoltaic capacity and 42.34 GWh of battery storage, optimizing costs to reach 92.21 €/MWh. This result underscores the potential of photovoltaic systems in contributing to Italy's targets on renewable energy.

Pierro et al. [18] focuses attention on solar regulation and the potential of PV to provide ancillary services mitigating the increased demand/supply imbalance caused by the inherent intermittency and variability of VRE sources. In this study, the energy-flexible PV fleet with BESS, required to reduce the Italian imbalance by 36 % compared to 2016, is sized so that the level of curtailment stays at a constant and reasonable value (6 % in this case) at the current and future penetration levels. Another important finding is that costs associated to solar regulation are comparable or even lower than that resulting from PV power forecast uncertainty and the current imbalance regulation strategy that relies on fast thermoelectric generators. Pierro et al. [19] further explore the possibility of reducing solar-induced imbalance by remotely controlling PV plants using smart inverters. A strategy involving a more accurate PV and net load power forecast is proposed and deemed able to limit the impact of imbalance, while a properly sized energy-flexible PV fleet with BESS, which the TSO can remotely control and proactively curtail, has the potential to entirely eliminate it, thus providing operational certainty. The original use of energy-flexible PV systems with BESS as an imbalance regulation instrument and the reduction of imbalance itself are of great relevance for our work, which aims at improving the efficiency and reliability of solar resources.

As far as high-VRE penetration is concerned, Switzerland provides a very interesting case, as they are set to phase out their nuclear power by 2044, as part of their Energy Strategy 2050 [20]. Consistently with this objective, Remund et al. [21] explore the potential of PV to significantly contribute to Switzerland's transition to a renewable future, while also being economically viable. The study analyzed different configurations involving PV systems, BESS, and implicit storage technologies, leveraging Switzerland's flexible hydropower capabilities. Despite challenges such as limited wind power and reduced PV output during winter, the study concluded that solutions heavily reliant on renewable energy, with PV playing a central role, are both physically and economically feasible for Switzerland. The operational costs associated with these scenarios were found to be reasonable when compared to current wholesale market prices in Switzerland, even during periods of international tension where energy prices might not fully reflect environmental or strategic considerations. These findings confirm the viability of transitioning to high levels of renewable energy in a country with diverse resources and constraints but also demonstrate that such a transition can be achieved at reasonable costs, providing valuable context and inspiration for similar endeavors in other regions.

Shifting our scope to Europe's ambitious renewable energy plan, known as REPowerEU, an interesting study conducted by van Eldik and van Sark [22] introduces a model called the "Pan-European Intermittent Renewable Overbuilding and Curtailment Optimization Model" (PEIROCOM). The primary goal of this model is to determine the optimal combination of PV and wind power, coupled with various storage

technologies to ensure a stable and reliable power supply. The authors utilized projections of electricity demand and interconnection capacities for the year 2030 from the European Resource Adequacy Assessment (ERAA). The PEIROCOM model optimizes the deployment of both production and storage capacities, as well as the hourly distribution of stored energy and interconnections across 37 European countries and neighboring regions. One of the key concepts introduced in this study is the "firm kWh premium", originally proposed by Perez et al. [23]. This concept quantifies the additional cost required to transform VRE into firm power. The study found that in a scenario where only lithium-ion batteries are used, the firm kWh premium is estimated to be 3.91, with 50 % of generated electricity being curtailed. However, when hydrogen storage is incorporated into the system, the firm kWh premium decreases to 2.90, and curtailment drops to 31 %. This research serves as a critical foundation for our study, introducing the theme of high PV penetration at a continental level and focusing on strategies to mitigate intermittency and ensure grid stability.

The topic of VRE optimization is widely explored also outside the confines of Europe. The previously mentioned work by Perez et al. [23] details a case study in Minnesota, then extended to the Midcontinent Independent System Operator (MISO) region by Perez [24], demonstrating that strategic overbuilding of PV capacity, coupled with dynamic curtailment, can result in the achievement of firm, high-penetration-ready PV generation at costs comparable to or even lower than conventional generation methods, especially when combined optimally with wind generation. This research explores various assumptions regarding future technology costs, sector electrification, and technological diffusion. The studies find that achieving 100 % renewable generation by 2050 without subsidies could be economically feasible, with costs comparable to current wholesale electricity generation costs in the MISO system. Additionally, the cost-effectiveness of the overbuilding and curtailment PV generation strategy is highlighted, as well as the potential for further cost reduction through hybridization of wind and PV systems. The researchers project that by 2050, declining costs of solar PV compared to wind could lead to solar PV serving a larger percentage of the load in most regions and cost scenarios. These insights align closely with the investigation into firm renewable generation, serving as a strong foundation for our work in the context of the Rome Technopole.

A particularly interesting variation on firm PV plants is proposed in [25] that presents a case study in Northern China for which PV is coupled with pumped-hydro storage (PHS), a long-term storage solution presented as an alternative to BESS. Concerning long-term storage, Yang et al. [26] explore the role of combining short- and long-term solutions, specifically batteries and hydrogen, in reducing the cost of firm PV generation.

Such studies are instrumental in illustrating the range of technological options and strategies available to support firm PV. Perez et al. [3] propose a novel approach named "firm solar forecast" aimed at optimizing the operation of overbuilt solar power plants. The strategy involves utilizing accurately predicted solar power generation alongside appropriately sized storage systems to compensate for any inaccuracies in the forecasts, thus eliminating uncertainties related to balancing the load on the power grid caused by fluctuations in solar energy production. The authors argue that this approach, while economically justified on its own merits, serves as an effective initial step towards achieving high solar energy penetration into the grid, where firm power generation becomes essential. They use the "New York Independent System Operator" (NYISO) as a case study to analyze the current and projected costs of firm forecasts in various scenarios within each electrical region of the ISO, comparing centralized and decentralized production methods and evaluating the impact of load flexibility. Furthermore, the study indicates that the impact of geographic dispersion on the operational costs can be mitigated by focusing on generating firm power rather than solely relying on forecasts. These findings suggest that implementing locally resilient solutions within specific electrical sub-

regions could be a viable option at a modest cost premium, shedding light on the feasibility of achieving very high PV penetration. This aligns closely with the objectives of the present investigation into renewable energy strategies. In two interesting works, Keeratimahat et al. [27] and Boland [28] paint a picture of the Australian framework in the field of firm PV generation. Keeratimahat et al. investigate the feasibility of utility-scale PV plants in providing more predictable and firm dispatchable generation by analyzing historical data from several Australian utility plants. The study highlights that achieving firm dispatch from solar generation is challenging due to the high uncertainty associated with its output, even when weather conditions are known, necessitating significant levels of curtailment, which can impact the overall efficiency and economic viability of PV generation. Boland indicates that, as of 2022, the installed capacity of solar farms in Australia reached almost 11 GW, representing a significant portion of the country's total electricity generation capacity, with a prevalence of oversized solar fields. In this case, this is intended as the capacity of the solar panels exceeding that of the inverters used to convert the solar energy into usable electricity, creating what is known as an "inverter-limited application". Despite this limitation, the author suggests that this practice is economically justifiable under the current rules set by the Australia Energy Market Operator (AEMO) and represent an initial step towards achieving firm VRE power generation.

Tapachès et al. [29] defines pathways to achieve electricity generation autonomy on Reunion Island, a French overseas territory in the Indian Ocean. The approach adopted is based on a least-cost firm power generation strategy, which involves spatial distribution, overbuilding PV capacity, and curtailment, along with the sizing of a storage system. The study demonstrates that compared to a traditional approach that does not consider overbuilding PV capacity, the use of implicit storage significantly reduces the Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) en route for 100 % electricity generation from PV. A roadmap is outlined based on LCOE versus Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) analysis, indicating that the most cost-effective path involves implementing firm power forecasts initially, followed by transitioning to 100 % PV generation during daytime hours, and eventually completely replacing coal-fired plants with solar generation.

Furthermore, a work by Yang et al. [30] presents a simulation case study focusing on a 1-MWp PV plant, meeting an annual energy demand equivalent to a 0.17 MW constant load, located in the cold climate region of Harbin, China. The authors demonstrate that a 3x-oversized PV plant, coupled with battery storage and proactive curtailment, can reduce the cost of firm generation by 79.67 % compared to a scenario with no overbuilding, but with proactive curtailment and larger battery storage.

This research is highly relevant to our analysis, as it offers valuable insights into scenarios of high PV power penetration across different regions and climates, along with a number of critical issues that may arise when planning the implementation of an energy-flexible PV strategy with BESS and, ultimately, firm PV generation within the Rome Technopole context.

The theme of PV generation forecast, briefly touched upon in the cited literature, is another crucial element for the integration of solar energy into the electrical grid. As previously discussed, the issue of solar-induced imbalances can threaten the stability of the electrical system, as well as increasing costs. Thus, improving the accuracy of forecasting assumes a pivotal role as solar energy penetration increases.

The firm solar forecast approach is adopted in [31] where overbuilding and proactive curtailment are combined with a physical model chain to enhance the accuracy of converting weather forecasts into PV power forecasts. This method was tested across major cities in north-eastern China, resulting in a firm forecast premium ranging from 1.68 to 2.48.

A study conducted in Italy by Pierro et al. [32] evaluates how PV power forecast accuracy affects economic outcomes under the "single pricing" scheme employed in the Italian dispatch market from the

viewpoint of individual PV producers, often overlooked in favor of the TSO's. Surprisingly, despite the crucial need for accurate solar power forecasting to balance supply and demand effectively, the research suggests that higher revenues can result from lower quality forecasts under the existing market system. These findings highlight the need for a new market pricing rule and innovative actions to mitigate the negative effects of current regulations and improve the integration of solar energy into the electrical grid.

Recently, Pierro et al. [33] proposes a methodology to evaluate the potential for reducing imbalances and increasing system flexibility through advanced forecasting techniques and improvements to the Italian grid. Different forecasting methods are combined to predict the day-ahead supply from dispatchable generators, indicating a substantial potential for reducing imbalances by 60.3 % and flexibility requirements by 47.5 % compared to baseline forecasts. In contrast, the forecasts provided by the TSO offer limited margin for reducing imbalances through improved accuracy. However, a more substantial reduction can be achieved by addressing grid constraints between different market zones, which should therefore be considered of utmost importance in transitioning to a VRE-based energy production system.

Perez et al. [34] take a step further by introducing the concept of perfect forecast, serving both as a validation metric for forecasting accuracy and as an operational strategy for the growth of VRE generation into power grids. The study also analyzes the costs associated with correcting imperfect predictions, that include expenses related to backup storage and output curtailment needed to address over or under predictions. The authors conclude that achieving perfect predictions, which means fully eliminating uncertainty for grid operators, is feasible at a relatively small operational cost. Furthermore, the researchers claim, a perfect forecast strategy, combined with optimized least-cost storage and management of overbuild/curtailment, represents an effective initial step in a long-term strategy to cost-effectively transform variable PV generation into a reliable and dispatchable generation source capable of replacing conventional generation methods.

These works provide invaluable perspective on some of the main issues that need to be addressed in order to improve VRE generation forecasts and the potential that these hold for the growth of VRE penetration in power grids. Methodologies are also presented that serve as an essential starting point for our research.

From a purely economic standpoint, the work by Rey-Costa et al. [35] discusses the increasing viability of transitioning to 100 % renewable energy systems due to the decreasing costs of solar photovoltaic (PV) and wind power technologies, focusing on the Australian National Electricity Market. It's noted that without battery storage, meeting 100 % of the energy demand between 2010 and 2020 requires generating approximately four times the actual load, albeit at a cost 28 % lower than recent wholesale electricity prices. However, with the addition of 1–8 h of battery storage, the average production cost decreases significantly, by 55 % compared to recent prices.

An interesting study by Yang et al. [36] develops a new mathematical optimization model aimed at calculating the "firm kWh premium", which serves as an indicator of the cost-effectiveness of implementing technologies that enable reliable power delivery from renewable sources, particularly solar power. The authors examine several factors that influence this parameter, including future price trends of PV panels and batteries, the choice of battery model, and inter-annual variability in solar resources. Through optimization, it is found that, under current cost structures, achieving a low firm kWh premium remains challenging, particularly in certain locations like northern China, and the investment cost of PV and battery storage need to drop under 250 \$/kW and 40 \$/kWh respectively to reach grid parity.

Finally, as previously mentioned, Remund et al. [37] note a misalignment between the overbuild/curtailment strategy and current market rules, that may not necessarily serve the interests of VRE producers. The authors suggest that current market designs, which rely on marginal energy production signals, are insufficient, and advocate for

market rules grounded in the capacity of firmly enabled VREs, rather than solely focusing on their energy output. Ultimately, the study argues for an economic model that adapts to the variability of VRE resources, rather than forcing them to conform to existing market structures. The need is emphasized for market rules that incentivize the transformation of VRE resources into firm power generation, thereby ensuring the reliability and stability of renewable energy grids.

On this topic, Kihlstrom et al [38] point out that PV growth still heavily depends on government intervention, mainly due to inadequate market structures and regulatory uncertainty. The nature of these interventions, the author notes, is often short-term and fragmented, which severely hinders the development of a self-sustaining market.

Recently, researchers have proposed new market designs that integrate renewable energy and flexibility technologies. This is the case for Di Foggia et al. [39], who advocate for decoupling renewables from fossil fuel pricing, enabling the trading of flexibility products (e.g., storage), and promoting decentralized energy management. This approach implies gradually developing a new energy market paradigm, rather than applying incremental adjustments to the existing one.

The analysis of energy markets and their influence on the growth of VRE penetration is central to our work, as the application of a flexible photovoltaic strategy to the Rome Technopole will undoubtedly have to confront this reality and the challenges it poses.

As discussed so far, the idea of powering the Rome Technopole through an energy-flexible PV strategy with BESS, ultimately aiming at firm PV generation, builds upon the concepts of overbuilding and curtailment. The project can only be economically feasible by assessing the correct balance between conventional battery energy storage and implicit storage and needs a shift of mentality in accepting curtailment not as a loss, but rather as instrumental to increasing the efficiency of the strategy. Other crucial elements to the success of the idea lie in the field of generation forecasts and in how the overbuilding/curtailment approach fits into the energy market rules. Since most of these factors are expected to change and evolve in the coming years, we propose to draw a roadmap for our project, setting self-production milestones for 2030, 2040 and 2050. Due to the Rome Technopole still being under construction, the analysis has been performed on the Engineering Faculty of the University of Rome Tor Vergata which, thanks to having a similar function, can be considered a good benchmark. This project will allow the Rome Technopole to be a pioneer application in high VRE penetration, resulting in a reduced environmental impact along with a reduction in LCOE.

The cited literature presents several case studies spanning different areas of the world (see Table 1 and 2 for a summary).

The novelty of this work with respect to these lies in showcasing the optimization process used to determine the most cost-effective PV and

storage capacities for different scenarios of self-production. The process and parameters involved in the calculation of the LCOE are presented, along with an analysis of the available surfaces and the evaluation of the PBP for each scenario.

While many studies have explored the cost-effective sizing and placement of PV and BESS systems, this work is distinctive in that it applies an energy-flexible PV strategy with BESS, incorporating both explicit storage and implicit storage via curtailment, to a real-world case study in Italy, namely, the Rome Technopole. Unlike previous studies that focus on theoretical or isolated system configurations, this work proposes a stepwise roadmap (2030–2040–2050) aligned with national energy policies. Moreover, it includes a comprehensive economic analysis (LCOE and PBP) and considers surface availability constraints, all based on real energy usage data from the Engineering Faculty of the University of Rome Tor Vergata.

The main contributions of this work are:

- The development of an energy-flexible PV strategy with BESS, integrating both explicit and implicit storage, to achieve firm PV generation in an urban campus setting.
- The application of this strategy to a real electricity demand profile (2013–2021) from the University of Rome Tor Vergata, serving as a benchmark for the future Rome Technopole.
- A cost-optimization model that determine the optimal PV and BESS sizing for four self-production targets (2023, 2030, 2040, 2050), aiming to minimize LCOE.
- A comparative analysis of PBP under future cost projections (2023–2050) to assess the economic feasibility of the proposed configurations.
- A contribution to national and EU-level discussions on the viability and market integration of firm PV generation strategies.

The Rome Technopole project

Rome Technopole [40] represents a collaborative R&D initiative involving the public and private Universities of Lazio, EPR, industrial associations, local enterprises, the Lazio Region, the Municipality of Rome, and regional Chambers of Commerce. Its goal is to catalyze a significant advancement in the Lazio Region's innovation sector, focusing on sustainable development, smart specialization, industrial revitalization, and excellence in three key thematic areas:

- Energy Transition;
- Digital Transition;
- Health & Bio-Pharma.

Table 1
Summary of studies addressing the techno-economic literature.

Reference	Case Study / Scope	PV/BESS Sizing	Economic Metrics (LCOE, PBP)	Explicit + Implicit Storage	Real Demand Profile	Roadmap	Novelty / Focus
[9]	Simulated system	✓	✓ (Unavailability index)	✓	✗	✗	Identifies “critical storage zone”
[10]	USA (regional)	✓	Partial (system cost)	✓	✗	✗	Early proposal of implicit storage concept
[20]	Switzerland (national)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	High PV scenario using flexible hydro
[23]	MISO (USA)	✓	✓	✓	Partial	✗	Overbuild-curtailment strategy validated
[28]	Reunion Island	✓	✓ (LCOE vs CAPEX)	✓	✓	✓	Stepwise firm PV transition
[29]	Harbin, China	✓	✓ (79.67 % cost reduction)	✓	✓	✗	Analysis of oversizing + storage
[34]	Australia (NEM)	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	Storage-less PV requires 4 × overbuild
[35]	Northern China	✓	✓ (“firm kWh premium”)	✓	✗	✗	Optimization under tech cost assumptions
This Work	Rome Technopole / UniTorVergata	✓ (cost-optimal)	✓ (LCOE + PBP)	✓ (BESS + curtailment)	✓ (2013–2021 data)	✓ (2030–2040–2050)	First real-case roadmap with flexible PV strategy in Italy

Table 2
Summary of studies addressing curtailment, forecasting, and market literature.

Reference	Focus Area	Curtailment Strategy	Forecasting	Market Integration	Notable Contribution
[4]	PV dispatchability	✓	✓	✗	Introduces key enablers (ESS, forecast, curtailment)
[5]	Storage technologies	✗	✗	✗	Overview of ESS options (thermal, BESS, PHS, CAES)
[12–14]	Reframing curtailment	✓	✗	✓	Defines curtailment as unused potential, not waste
[15–18]	Grid balancing (Italy)	✓	✓	✓	Flexible PV + BESS for imbalance regulation
[21,22]	Firm kWh premium, PEIROCOM	✓	✗	✓	Continental-scale optimization with cost premiums
[26]	Firm solar forecast	✓	✓	Partial	Combines forecast + storage for firm output
[3]	Utility-scale dispatch	✓	✗	✗	Utility PV requires high curtailment for firm output
[27]	Inverter-limited PV (Australia)	Partial	✗	✓	Overbuilding justifiable under AEMO market design
[30–32]	Forecast & imbalance	✗	✓	✓	Advanced forecasting reduces imbalance by 60 %
[33]	Perfect forecast concept	✓	✓	✓	Operational cost of forecast correction is low
[36]	Market design critique	✓	✗	✓	Market rules penalize overbuild-curtailment strategies
[37]	Policy dependency	✗	✗	✓	PV expansion still relies heavily on public support
[38]	Energy market reform	✗	✗	✓	Advocates for trading of flexibility and decoupling fossil indexing
This Work	Energy-flexible PV + market alignment (Italy)	✓ (as implicit storage)	✓ (role of forecast emphasized)	✓ (adaptation to market rules + roadmap)	Real-case application with BESS + curtailment + roadmap; addresses curtailment mindset shift and regulatory barriers in Italy

The primary objective of the Rome Technopole project is to establish a dynamic regional innovation ecosystem aimed at achieving three key macro-goals for Lazio:

1. Facilitate the strategic repositioning of regional industrial and productive entities towards segments and markets offering higher added value. This involves adapting cutting-edge technologies and expertise to enhance competitiveness.
2. Position Lazio as a leading European hub for innovation with a global reach, fostering international collaboration and recognition.
3. Drive Lazio's internationalization efforts by leveraging the renewed competitive strength of its industrial sector, strategically targeting key markets for sustained growth and expansion.

Within the Energy Transition thematic area (Spoke 1, FP1), the project titled “100 % Renewable for Rome Technopole” (RES4TECH) was introduced, and this paper presents the findings of the research.

Materials and methods

Our study focuses on fine-tuning solar panel (PV) systems and battery storage (BESS) setups to address the energy needs of the Engineering Macro-area at the University of Rome Tor Vergata. Our primary aim is to achieve this while simultaneously minimizing the LCOE. To accomplish this objective, we adopted a comprehensive approach, considering various target self-production values. Each of these targets necessitates an accurate assessment of the optimal balance between PV oversizing (OVS), BESS size, and the resulting LCOE.

In view of the dynamic interplay between technological progress and economic factors, our analysis goes beyond current considerations. We integrate a forward-looking perspective by taking into account the variation of parameters over time and running simulations from 2023 to 2050. This time dimension ensures that our solutions remain adaptable and viable in the face of changing circumstances.

Our main goal is to create a roadmap for the expansion of energy capacity in the Macro area, aiming for a self-production rate of ~ 100 %. We must ensure that the LCOE remains below the threshold set by the Italian National Unique Price of energy (PUN), which was 127 €/MWh in 2023 [41].

Here we focus on the three main components of the optimization process. Firstly, we introduce the concept of firm PV power generation, emphasizing the reliability and consistency of energy output essential for meeting the Macro-area's demands. Subsequently, we delved into the design process for generating a sample input dataset crucial for

conducting comprehensive simulations. Finally, we detail the algorithm used to methodically lower the cost of energy (LCOE), guaranteeing the economic viability of our suggested solutions.

Through this structured approach, our study aims not only to offer theoretical insights but also to provide practical strategies for achieving sustainable and cost-effective energy solutions tailored to the specific needs of the Macro-area of Engineering.

Firm PV power generation

The strategy behind firm PV generation [3,30,37] involves proactively curtailing production to precisely match electrical demand. While this strategy may not seem intuitive and contrasts with the current perception of solar production, it is the key element for a low-cost PV production strategy. Instead, entirely meeting the electrical demand through PV without curtailment requires a very large storage capacity that drastically increases the cost of system. In the firm PV generation, the concept of implicit storage is introduced by oversizing the photovoltaic generation, thereby reducing the required battery capacity and consequently lowering the final system cost. However, oversizing the PV plant results in an increase in electricity production compared to actual demand. This excess production must be proactively curtailed to avoid congestion in the grid. In this study the optimal balance between PV plant and battery capacity reduction is determined by minimizing the LCOE.

Input dataset

In order to apply the firm PV power generation to the case study, various inputs are required for the period spanning from 2013 to 2021, including:

- Solar irradiance and weather data set;
- Electricity demand
- Cost learning curves

Solar irradiance and weather datasets

Two primary sources were used to collect solar irradiance data: the “Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service” (CAMS) [42] and the ESTER Laboratory (Solar Energy Test and Research), located within the Macro-area [43–45]. CAMS provides irradiation data derived from satellite observations for specific geographic locations and time periods. In this work, data were obtained for the period from January 1, 2013, to

December 31, 2021, with hourly resolution. ESTER's data, on the other hand, are acquired by ground-based pyranometers, with both one-minute and hourly measurements.

Since the data from ESTER Lab present gaps due to sensor malfunctions within the considered time frame, it was decided to use them only as a comparison parameter for the CAMS dataset. In literature, the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) associated with the comparison between a dataset of irradiance estimated through satellite data and a dataset of irradiance measured by ground-installed sensors is typically reported to range between 50 and 100 $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ [46].

The results from our comparison over the years 2013 to 2021 highlight the reliability of data obtained from satellites. Throughout the comparison period, the RMSE consistently remained below 55 $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, except for 2015 (Table 3 and Fig. 1). During this particular year, the ESTER station encountered heightened occurrences of sensor and apparatus malfunctions.

Temperature and wind speed measured at the ESTER Lab were integrated with data from station AL001 of ARPA Lazio, situated within the CNR's Tor Vergata site [47]. Since the two measurement points are slightly distant, the first step was to compare the data between the two laboratories. It was noticed that the temperature measured by the AL001 weather station is almost always lower than that measured by the ESTER weather station (Fig. 2).

The data from the AL001 weather station was therefore corrected. The correction was made by correlating the two databases and finding a linear fit. The linear fit provided the equation correlating the two datasets, which is of the form:

$$T_{AL001,fit} = 0.932 \cdot T_{ESTER} - 0.329 \quad (1)$$

The corrected temperature was then obtained using the equation:

$$T_{AL001,corr} = T_{AL001} + (T_{ESTER} - T_{AL001,fit}) \quad (2)$$

Once the correction was applied, its effectiveness was verified by checking the correlation between the corrected AL001 data and those of ESTER. As seen from the figure, a correlation coefficient close to 1 was obtained (Fig. 3).

Electricity demand

The data concerning the hourly electricity consumption at the Macro-area of Engineering was only available for the year 2019 (Fig. 4).

Since meteorological data span from 2013 to 2021 (included), we conducted an extrapolation of the hourly electricity consumption [48,49]. This extrapolation process considered consumption variations with temperature and the associated day of the week, thus covering the missing years.

Through statistical analysis, it became evident that the baseline load required over 55 % of the annual hours, approximately 200 kW, with loads exceeding 1 MW being rare.

To understand the relationship between average daily energy usage, days of the week, and average daily temperatures, we first calculated the daily energy usage and temperature for each day of the year. Following this, data for each day of the week were extracted from the two datasets

for correlation using quadratic fits. Our observation revealed that on weekdays (Monday to Friday), the load increases as the average daily temperature deviates from 17 °C. The fit levels off for Saturdays and becomes nearly horizontal for Sunday, when the educational and research activities are reduced or stopped and then only the baseline load remains, as evident from (Fig. 5).

The quadratic fits for average daily load and temperature are used to calculate the hourly load for a specific hour (h), day (d), and week (w) in one of the missing years $P_{year}(h, d, w)$. This is accomplished by scaling the load associated with the same moment in 2019 $P_{2019}(h, d, w)$ by a coefficient obtained as follows: the fit for the day of the week d under consideration (FIT_d) is computed for the average temperature associated with the selected day and week ($T_{year}(d, w)$), and is then divided by the average load of the corresponding day in 2019 ($P_{dailyavg,2019}(d, w)$).

$$P_{year}(h, d, w) = P_{2019}(h, d, w) \frac{FIT_d(T_{year}(d, w))}{P_{dailyavg,2019}(d, w)} \quad (3)$$

This equation is used to calculate the hourly load for the missing years. The results of this procedure are very encouraging; comparing the extrapolated data with the available data, an increase of 10 % in the average load and energy consumed annually has been observed. Regarding the maximum power, there's an increase of about 25 %, while a decrement of 50 % for the minimum (Table 4). This result can be attributed to the quadratic fit applied. For example, if a high load occurs at external average temperatures far from the abscissa associated with the vertex of the parabola used as a fit, the deviation will be more pronounced. However, the obtained result does not differ significantly from the reference year (2019) as the average power and the energy consumed annually are minimally affected. This can be also seen by the comparison between the duration curve of consumed electrical power for 2019 (Fig. 6a) and for the extrapolation (Fig. 6b).

Cost learning curves

The scenarios examined in this study is based on PV and BESS costs in 2023, with consideration extending to 2030, 2040, and 2050. These simulations leveraged the CAPEX values for PV and BESS provided by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) [50]. NREL delineates three distinct scenarios: conservative, moderate, and advanced. For the year 2023, the conservative values were adopted, while projections for future years were based on the moderate hypothesis.

Table 5 resume the assumed values and Fig. 7 illustrates the CAPEX trends for PV and BESS across the three scenarios.

Optimization process – LCOE minimization

Our strategy in this research seeks to transform solar (PV) power generation into a reliable and cost-efficient energy source available 24/7, 365 days a year. This method involves enlarging the PV system beyond the usual size to reduce the battery storage size needed. To do this effectively, we engage in an optimization process aimed at striking the perfect balance between lowering the necessary battery size and increasing the PV system's capacity. By reducing the cost of energy (LCOE) through this dual approach, we make the system more economically feasible and ensure consistent energy production, even when sunlight is scarce.

The optimization methodology utilized in this study is based on a brute-force approach, developed by the authors in MATLAB, which systematically explores the entire solution space to determine the optimal configuration for both PV and BESS capacity. This process involves a comprehensive evaluation of all conceivable combinations of PV oversizing (OVS) and BESS values within predefined intervals. By thoroughly traversing this solution space, the algorithm meticulously analyzes various configurations, enabling a comprehensive assessment of the trade-offs between OVS and BESS capacity.

The approach adopted in this algorithm is the same as that used in

Table 3
Results of the comparison between the irradiance datasets of ESTER and CAMS.

Year	RMSE ($\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$)
2013	46.3679
2014	45.7697
2015	81.4921
2016	45.5433
2017	52.1049
2018	52.5372
2019	47.6589
2020	46.1214
2021	45.7950

Fig. 1. GHI measured by ESTER and CAMS for 2015 a) and 2016b).

Fig. 2. Comparison of temperature datasets from the ESTER station (red) and the AL001 station (black). The enlargement highlights the differences between the two datasets.

the authors' previous work [17], where all the details regarding cost assumptions and are provided. The Levelized Cost of Electricity (LCOE) is calculated using the following equation:

[51] while the cost of energy delivered by storage ($LCOS_{flexPV}$) is calculated using the detailed methodology developed in [52] which accounts for actual battery usage, including calendar aging, degradation

$$LCOE = \frac{[En_{PV2L} \cdot LCOE_{firmPV} + En_{BESS2L} \cdot LCOS_{firmPV} + En_{wind-imp} \cdot price_{wind-imp} + En_{res-load} \cdot price_{En}]}{En_{load}} \quad (4)$$

where En_{PV2L} , En_{BESS2L} , $En_{res-load}$ represent the self-consumed PV energy, the energy supplied by storage, and the residual demand that must be covered by other dispatchable generators at the market price ($price_{En}$) and En_{load} is the total energy demand.

$LCOE_{firmPV}$ and $LCOS_{firmPV}$ refer to the levelized costs of PV and storage, respectively, considering only the portion of PV generation used to meet the firm demand. $En_{wind-imp}$ and $price_{wind-imp}$ indicate the imported wind energy and its associated price.

The production cost of PV ($LCOE_{firmPV}$) is computed as described in

through full equivalent cycles, and the resulting variable operation and maintenance (O&M) costs.

The algorithm, reported as diagram flow in Fig. 8, begins by iteratively adjusting OVS values from minimum to maximum while simultaneously varying BESS values from maximum to minimum. Each combination of OVS and BESS is carefully evaluated to meet the required level of self-production (SP), defined as the ratio between the electricity generated by energy-flexible PV systems with BESS and the total electricity demand ($0 \leq SP \leq 1$).

Battery capacity is expressed as the "number of daily electric demand

Fig. 3. Correlation between AL001 temperature (corrected) and ESTER, colour-legend represents the point density.

Fig. 4. Electricity demand of the Macro-area of Engineering in 2019.

to be stored" (NDY), indicating the consecutive days the system can operate solely on stored energy without relying on external sources. This parameter is essential for assessing the system's resilience and autonomy during periods of limited PV energy generation.

The algorithm iteratively explores all combinations of OVS and NDY within the defined limits. It starts with the lowest OVS value and the highest NDY value, calculating the corresponding SP. If the resulting SP falls within $\pm 0.5\%$ of the target, the model proceeds to evaluate the LCOE. If the SP does not meet the target, the algorithm decreases NDY and repeats the calculation. Once the minimum NDY value is reached, the process continues with the next OVS value, resetting NDY to its initial value, and so on.

This tolerance accounts for uncertainties in demand and generation, ensuring the system remains robust under slightly varying conditions.

The study explores SP values within specific ranges to account for variability in electricity demand and generation.

In our study we explore the different SP values within 50 % and 100 %, specifically 65, 70, 80 90 %.

Results and discussion

This paper explores different scenarios simulating the coverage of electricity demand at the Macro-area of Engineering of the University of Rome Tor Vergata using photovoltaics and batteries. Various CAPEX costs for PV and BESS were considered, drawing upon data provided by NREL, as elaborated in the preceding section. The simulations encompassed different levels of VRE self-production in meeting electricity demand, ranging from 50 % to 100 %. Moreover, the results elucidate

Fig. 5. Correlation between average daily load and average daily temperature in 2019.

Table 4
2019 Electric demand compared to the extrapolated data (2013–2021).

		2019	2013–2021	Δ (%)
Average power	kW	410	440	7.3
Maximum power	kW	1367	1700	24.4
Minimum power	kW	170	83.5	-50.9
Standard deviation	kW	266	297	11.7
First quartile	kW	220	225	2.3
Second quartile	kW	247	310	25.5
Third quartile	kW	560	597	6.6
Average annual consumed energy	GWh	3.59	3.88	7.3

the trend of LCOE concerning VRE penetration.

The calculation of LCOE was accompanied by determining the daily electric demand to be stored and the hours of operation for BESS. LCOE scenarios were computed as a weighted average of the constituent elements involved in the overall energy demand:

- The energy supplied to the grid by the batteries, multiplied by the Levelized Cost of Storage (LCOS) of the batteries.
- Any remaining electricity demand, if applicable, multiplied by the PUN.
- PV production utilized to fulfill the load or recharge the storage, multiplied by the LCOE of PV, which considers the requisite proactive curtailment.

Furthermore, an assessment of the available surfaces within the faculty premises was conducted to determine their extent, exposure, and any shading. Finally, an economic analysis was performed for all

simulated cases to calculate the PBP.

Before proceeding with the simulations, the minimum value of SP achievable by a photovoltaic system with peak power equal to that needed to produce the energy consumed by the Macro-area without incorporating storage was verified. Table 6 and Fig. 9 show the outcomes of the analysis.

It can be noticed that without storage, to meet the electrical demand, it would be necessary to install a system of approximately 2.5 MWp, which, however, would only cover about 49 % of the electrical demand (SP = 49 %), while the remaining 51 % would need to be fed into the grid or cut off as it is produced when not needed. The corresponding LCOE for this setup is approximately €119/MWh.

These results underscore the critical importance of storage in aligning production with demand, thus minimizing reliance on the grid and ensuring optimal utilization of generated energy, in fact even increasing the OVS by 10 or 100 times the PV capacity the maximum SP achievable would be 56 %.

On the other hand, achieving SP = 100 % with a PV capacity sized to match annual demand (i.e., OVS = 1) would require an unrealistic battery capacity of approximately 3718.3 MWh (NDY = 350 days),

Table 5
CAPEX values used in the simulation.

Year	PV (€/kWp)	BESS (€/kWh)
2023	1037	312
2030	673	199
2040	613	175
2050	553	150

Fig. 6. Duration curves of electrical power consumption for the reference year (a) and for the extrapolated data of individual years (excluding 2019) along with the entire dataset (b).

Fig. 7. PV and BESS CAPEX trends (moderate hypothesis used), by NREL [50].

Fig. 8. Diagram flow of the algorithm.

Table 6

Maximum self-production without storage.

PV (kWp)	BESS (kWh)	SP (%)	OVS (-)	NDY (days)	Curtailement (%)	LCOE _{firm} (€/kWh)
2526	0	49	1	0	51	0.119

resulting in an LCOE of around €4.2/kWh. This value is clearly unsustainable, highlighting the need for a new methodology for sizing PV and BESS aimed at minimizing LCOE (Table 7).

Simulation results

As outlined in the methodology section, our simulations were conducted with varying degrees of self-production, ranging from 65 % to 100 %, while considering the CAPEX associated with both PV and BESS for the years 2023, 2030, 2040, and 2050. The outcomes of these simulations are summarized in Table 8. To facilitate a clearer interpretation of the data presented in Table 8, we have graphically depicted these results in Fig. 10.

It's important to remember that the capacity values of PV and BESS in Table 6 have been determined through a minimization algorithm. This algorithm aims to identify the minimal quantities of these two components that meet the required self-production while achieving the

Fig. 9. Daily energy balance without storage and without oversize.

Table 7
BESS capacity and LCOE for SP = 100 % without PV overbuild (OVS = 1).

PV _{cap} (MWp)	NDY (days)	BESS _{cap} (MWh)	Curtailement (%)	SP (%)	LCOE (€/kWh)
2.526	350	3718.27	0	100	4.2

lowest possible value of LCOE_{firm} among all combinations of PV and BESS.

The primary observation gleaned from our analysis (Fig. 10) pertains to the trend of LCOE_{firm} concerning self-production and CAPEX costs associated with PV and BESS. Across all cost time domain, a distinct dual pattern emerges for self-production levels below approximately 87 %, LCOE_{firm} has a linear trend; however, beyond this threshold, the slope of

the trend increases sharply. Notably, when focusing on the cost scenarios for the years 2030, 2040, and 2050, we observe that the slope of the linear trend (up to approximately 86 %) is very low.

This suggests that it is feasible to increase self-production to higher levels without incurring significant increments in LCOE. For instance, considering the year 2030, transitioning from a self-production level of 65 % to 80 % results in an LCOE increase of approximately 8 %. Further, extending to a self-production level of 87 %, the corresponding increase in LCOE would amount to about 12 % (LCOE = 0.095€/kWh, value extrapolated from the graph). However, beyond the 87 % threshold, the increments in LCOE become more pronounced. For instance, at a self-production level of 90 %, the increase in LCOE rises to approximately 27 % (at 100 % is 140 %).

Fig. 11 illustrates the relationship between Curtailement and OVS concerning SP. It's noticeable that up to an SP value of 80 %, both OVS

Table 8
Simulation results at different SP and Costs.

SP (%)	PV (kWp)	BESS (kWh)	OVS (-)	NDY (day)	Curt. (%)	LCOE _{firm} (€/kWh)			
						Year 2023	Year 2030	Year 2040	Year 2050
65	2300	2615	1.4	0.246	24	0.112	0.085	0.080	0.075
70	2476	3267	1.4	0.308	24	0.117	0.086	0.081	0.075
80	3031	4631	1.5	0.436	27	0.130	0.092	0.084	0.077
90	4547	6422	2	0.605	45	0.160	0.108	0.098	0.088
100	9754	16,467	3.9	1.55	72	0.317	0.208	0.186	0.165

Fig. 10. PV and BESS CAPEX trends (moderate hypothesis used), by NREL.

Fig. 13. OVS and NDY vs SP.

Fig. 11. Curtailment and OVS vs SP.

Fig. 12. Comparison between Curtailment for SP = 70 % and SP = 90 %.

and Curtailment exhibit a relatively consistent pattern. This suggests that the augmented capacity of the photovoltaic system resulting from oversizing predominantly boosts implicit storage in proportion to the SP increment. This becomes apparent when examining the Curtailment trend, which remains minimal during winter months but escalates during spring and summer (Fig. 12).

For SP values exceeding 80 %, the two curves in Fig. 11 diverge. This suggests that the overgeneration caused by OVS doesn't proportionately boost implicit storage, resulting in an increase in curtailing even during

winter months (see Fig. 12).

It is also interesting to compare the trends of NDY and OVS as a function of SP (Fig. 13). NDY essentially shows a trend with 2 slopes, the first, for SP < 90 %, much lower than the second for SP > 90 %. To better understand the meaning of these two slopes of NDY, they must be related to OVS. In fact, we argue that the oversize of the photovoltaic system is comparable to an implicit storage that assists the batteries in achieving a certain SP. It is obvious that the coverage of electrical demand, for SP less than 100 %, is the prerogative of daylight hours, and then in the case of residual charge, it covers nighttime load. From this perspective, the two slopes of NDY are explained; indeed, as SP increases (>90 %), the capacity of the batteries must increase to cover all nighttime hours, but at the same time, OVS must also increase significantly to reduce battery usage during the day.

Moreover, the findings from the simulations outlined in Table 6 served as the basis for crafting a strategic plan aimed at maximizing renewable energy integration within the Rome Technopole. This roadmap delineates four distinct steps (refer to Fig. 14), each marking a pivotal milestone towards attaining self-sufficiency in energy production.

The roadmap delineates self-production targets of 65 %, 80 %, 90 %, and 100 %, corresponding to the years 2023, 2030, 2040, and 2050, respectively. Additionally, it specifies the required capacities of PV and BESS, along with the associated LCOE, together with the average PUN for 2023.

From the roadmap, it is easy to deduce that the first three milestones are easily attainable by comparing the LCOE with the average PUN of 2023. However, concerning the 100 % of SP, we can notice that this milestone is not economically feasible due to the high LCOE (165€/MWh compared to 127€/MWh). Nevertheless, it is possible to calculate the

Fig. 14. Roadmap for Rome Technopole.

Fig. 15. Satellite image showing available surfaces in the Engineering Macro-area.

maximum SP achievable, whose LCOE matches the value of the PUN from Fig. 10. By intersecting the calculated LCOE for 2050 with the PUN value, it is obtained that the maximum achievable SP is 95.5 %.

Surface analysis

The subsequent step following the simulations involved assessing the availability of surfaces suitable for installing photovoltaic panels. We conducted a comprehensive analysis of all surfaces within the Macro-area, encompassing ground-level areas as well as solar pavements (Fig. 15). Potentially, there are around 110000 m² of usable spaces in the macro area (Table 9).

Subsequently, we transitioned to a more intricate analysis of these surfaces, filtering out those susceptible to shading throughout the year or those with suboptimal terrain conditions, among other factors. This process yielded approximately 65000 m² of suitable surfaces, more than adequate for our purposes.

Surface 1 and 2, presently designated as parking areas for student vehicles, collectively span approximately 4 ha. Given that about 4.5 MWp is necessary to attain a 90 % Self Production rate, it stands to reason that with optimal utilization of these surfaces, we could meet 90 % of the Macro-area electrical demand. To achieve a 100 % Self Production, however, approximately 10 MWp are required, a rather high value that would require a much more intensive, and almost total, exploitation of the available surfaces.

Economic feasibility (PBP)

Table 8 summarizes all the values obtained from the simulations,

Table 9

List of the available surfaces in the Macro area of Engineering.

Surface #	Extension (m ²)						
1	33,600	6	3800	11	500	16	610
2	7500	7	4700	12	1250	17	1460
3	11,000	8	4800	13	1900	18	1070
4	14,600	9	4800	14	1650	19	1050
5	7500	10	2000	15	2000	20	1500
21	1100	22	1650				

Table 10

LCOE comparison for firm PV generation and in 2023 and 2050.

SP	2023		2050	
	LCOE _{firm} (€/kWh)	LCOE (€/kWh)	LCOE _{firm} (€/kWh)	LCOE (€/kWh)
65	0.112	0.086	0.075	0.045
80	0.130	0.098	0.077	0.051
90	0.160	0.094	0.088	0.051
100	0.317	0.103	0.165	0.054

including PV and BESS capacities and the LCOE_{firm} for various SP values with varying assumed costs. In the calculation of LCOE-PV_{firm}, the weight of the lost electricity production compared to what could be produced if the inverter continuously followed the Maximum Power Point is crucial due to curtailment. Considering that currently in Italy it is not yet necessary to carry out curtailment to avoid disrupting the grid's balance, it is possible to evaluate the LCOE cost in the scenario where the unused energy produced by the photovoltaic system, which should be curtailed, is instead fed into the grid and compensated. The results of this analysis are presented in Table 10 for two typical years, 2023 and 2050.

Therefore, the cost of electricity produced by the system strongly depends on the grid's capacity to accept excess power flows. To assess the feasibility of implementing a firm PV system considering the current ability to feed surplus energy into the grid, it is necessary to compare the LCOE value with the tariff per kWh consumed at which energy is purchased from the grid by the user.

To understand the profitability of a potential investment in the

implementation of a Firm PV system, it is necessary to evaluate the Net Present Value (NPV) and the PBP associated with it. For the calculation of the NPV, a Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC) of 5 % was used, along with an electricity price currently paid by the University of Rome Tor Vergata equal to 0.12 €/kWh, a plant lifespan of 30 years, and a selling price of excess electricity produced equal to 0.1 €/kWh.

To assess the profitability of a potential investment in the implementation of a Firm PV system, it is necessary to evaluate the Net Present Value (NPV) and the Payback Period (PBP). The initial investment (I_0), serves as the baseline for these evaluations. For the discounted PBP assessment, the year in which the NPV changes sign, from negative to positive, has been identified.

The Internal Rate of Return (IRR) was calculated by assessing the WACC value that nullifies the NPV. The profitability analysis of the investments made shows that the implementation of a Firm PV system capable of ensuring a 65 % SP is already profitable today. Achieving an 80 % SP entails a discounted Payback Period of 28 years if implemented in 2023: despite the investment being characterized by a positive NPV, the payback time is too long, advising to wait until 2050 to implement such a firm PV system (Table 11).

Using the values associated with the purchase and sale prices of electricity mentioned earlier, achieving Self Productions greater than 80 % is currently not advisable.

Conclusions

This study highlights the possibility of solar panels and battery storage systems to fulfill the electricity needs of the Engineering Macro-area at the University of Rome Tor Vergata.

Through our simulations, we have evaluated the importance of storage in matching energy production with the load necessities and then the consumptions. This emphasizes the need to reduce dependence on external power grids and improve the efficiency of energy use. Our examination of the trends in the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) in relation to variable renewable energy (VRE) penetration provides insights into the financial aspects of varying levels of self-generated power, along with the investment required for solar panels and battery storage systems.

The strategic roadmap developed based on our findings outlines achievable milestones for reaching energy self-sufficiency at the Rome Technopole. While the roadmap indicates that significant progress can be made in attaining high levels of self production, nevertheless reaching 100 % of self production by 2050 poses economic challenges due to associated high LCOE values.

Moreover, our territorial analysis reveals wide available spaces for installing PV panels and presenting opportunities for further renewable energy integration. However, achieving higher self-production rates necessitates careful consideration of surface utilization and investment implications.

Economic feasibility assessments, including PBP and net present value NPV analyses, underscore the profitability of implementing firm PV systems up to certain self-production thresholds. Despite the profitability of systems ensuring a 65 % self-production rate, caution is warranted when considering higher self-production levels due to longer payback periods and current market conditions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Gianluigi Bovesecchi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Federico Andreozzi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marcello Petitta:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology,

Table 11

Economic parameters related to the profitability of the investment in a Firm PV plant.

SP	Cost	I_0 (M€)	NPV (M€)	NPV _{rel} (M€)	PBP (years)	PBP _{disc} (years)	IRR (%)
65	2023	3.88	3.32	0.856	7	11	13
65	2050	2	5.66	2.83	3.5	5	27
80	2023	5.65	0.27	0.05	12	28	6
80	2050	2.89	3.76	1.27	6	9	16
90	2023	8.24	-3.55	-	-	-	-
90	2050	4.16	1.51	0.36	9.5	17	8
100	2023	18.9	-17.2	-	-	-	-
100	2050	9.57	5.6	-	-	-	-

Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marco Piero:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Richard Perez:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Cristina Cornaro:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Cristina Cornaro reports financial support was provided by Rome Technopole. Reports a relationship with that includes: Has patent pending to. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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